

Photoenergy conversion in photogalvanic cell composed of methylene blue – Ascorbic acid system

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Abstract : Methylene blue dye is used to sensitize photo-reaction with ascorbic acid. The photogalvanic effect was studied in photogalvanic cell containing methylene blue – ascorbic acid system. The photopotential and photocurrent generated by the cell were 901.0 mV and 165.0 μ A, respectively. The effect of variation of different parameters like pH, temperature, light intensity, electrode area and diffusion length, on the electrical output of the cell were observed. Current-voltage characteristics of the cell has been observed. A mechanism for the generation of photocurrent in this photogalvanic cell in presence of methylene blue as a dye have also been studied. Efficiency of cell is determined in terms of fill factor, conversion efficiency and storage capacity.

Keywords : Methylene blue, conversion efficiency, fill factor, ascorbic acid.

Introduction

In the field of photochemical energy conversion, Becquerel^{1,2} observed the flow of current between two asymmetrical illuminated metal electrodes in presence of light. The photogalvanic effect was reported first of all by Rideal and Williams³ but it was systematically investigated by Rabinowitch^{4,5}. Hoffman and Lichtion⁷ have described various problems encountered in the development of this field. Later some interesting photogalvanic systems were reported by many workers time to time⁸⁻¹¹. Recently, we have reported some interesting photogalvanic systems with reasonably good amount of electrical output and storage capacity¹²⁻²¹. In order to reach a significant value of conversion efficiency and storage capacity, the present system i.e. methylene blue – ascorbic acid was taken in photogalvanic cell.

Results and discussion

Current-voltage (i-V) characteristics, fill factor, conversion efficiency and performance of the cell :

The short circuit current (i_{sc}) and the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of the photogalvanic cell were measured with a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed) and digital pH meter (keeping the other circuit open), respec-

tively. The current and potential values in between these two extreme values (V_{oc} and i_{sc}) were recorded with the help of a carbon pot (log 470 k) connected in the circuit of microammeter through which an external load was applied.

It was observed that i-V curve of the cell deviated from its ideal regular rectangular shape. A point on the i-V curve was determined where the product of potential and current was maximum and it was called power point.

The value of potential and current at the power point are represented as V_{pp} and i_{pp} respectively. With help of the i-V curve, the fill factor, and the conversion efficiency of the cell was determined as 0.46 and 0.837% respectively using the eqs. (i) and (ii) respectively.

$$\text{Fill factor} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (i)$$

$$\text{Conversion efficiency} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{10.4 \text{ (mW cm}^{-2}\text{)}} \times 100\% \quad (ii)$$

The performance of the cell was studied by applying the necessary external current and potential at the power point after removing the source of light. It was observed the cell can be used in the dark at its power point for 165.0 min.

Effect of diffusion path length and electroactive species :

Effect of diffusion path length on electrical output was observed by using H-cell of different path length. It was observed that there was a sharp increase in photocurrent (i_{\max}) in the first few minutes of illumination, and then there was gradual decrease to a stable value of photocurrent. This kind of behavior of the photocurrent indicates an initial rapid reaction followed by a slow rate determining step at a later stage. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of diffusion path length

Diffusion length	Maximum photocurrent	Equilibrium photocurrent	Rate of initial generation of current
D_L (mm)	i_{\max} (μA)	i_{eq} (μA)	($\mu\text{A min}^{-1}$)
35.0	185.0	164.0	12.33
40.0	191.0	164.0	12.73
45.0	195.0	165.0	13.00
50.0	200.0	166.0	13.33
55.0	204.0	167.0	13.60

[Methylene blue] = $3.20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$; [Ascorbic acid] = $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; pH = 13.2; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} .

On the basis of the effect of diffusing path length on the current parameters was observed as earlier by Kaneko and Yamada⁶. It may be concluded that the leuco form of dye itself and its leuco form are the main electroactive species at the illuminated and dark chambers, respectively. However, the reductant and their oxidized products behave as the electron carriers in the cell diffusing through the path.

Effect of methylene blue (MB) concentration :

Variation of dye concentration was studied by using different concentration of dye. It was observed that low concentration of dye (methylene blue) resulted into a fall in photopotential and photocurrent because fewer dye molecules were available for the excitation and consecutive donation of the electrons to the platinum electrode. The high concentration of dye resulted again into decrease in electrical output as the intensity of light reaching the dye molecules decreases near the electrode due to absorption of the major portion of light by dye molecules present in path. The results are given in Table 2.

Effect of variation of ascorbic acid concentration :

The effect of variation of reductant (ascorbic acid) concentration shows that the decrease in reductant (ascorbic

Table 2. Effect of methylene blue concentration

MB-ascorbic acid system	[Methylene blue] $\times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$				
	2.0	2.5	3.2	3.5	4.0
Photopotential (mV)	671.0	760.0	901.0	810.0	680.0
Photocurrent (μA)	112.0	130.0	165.0	142.0	118.0
Power (μW)	75.152	98.8	148.665	115.02	80.24

[Ascorbic acid] = $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; Temperature = 303 K, pH = 13.2; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} .

acid) concentration resulted into a fall in electrical output because fewer reductant molecules were available for electron donation to the dye molecule. Similarly, the increase in concentration of ascorbic acid also resulted into a fall in electrical output because the large number of reductant molecule may prevent the dye molecule from reaching the electrode in the desired time. The results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of ascorbic acid concentration

MB-ascorbic acid system	[Ascorbic acid] $\times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$				
	4.0	4.2	4.8	5.2	5.6
Photopotential (mV)	688.0	809.0	901.0	822.0	703.0
Photocurrent (μA)	116.0	125.0	165.0	134.0	120.0
Power (μW)	79.808	101.25	148.665	110.148	84.36

[Methylene blue] = $3.20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; pH = 13.2; Temperature = 303 K.

Effect of variation of pH :

It was observed that there was an increase in electrical output of the cell with the increase in pH value up to a maximum at pH 13.2. On further increase in pH, there was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent.

It was observed that the pH for the optimum condition has a relation with pK_a of the reductant and the desired pH is higher than the pK_a value ($\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$). The reason may be the availability of reductant in its anionic form which is in a better donor form. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of pH

MB-ascorbic acid system	pH				
	12.4	12.8	13.2	13.6	14.00
Photopotential (mV)	715.0	802.0	901.0	814.0	722.0
Photocurrent (μA)	110.0	130.0	165.0	132.0	115.0
Power (μW)	78.65	104.0	148.665	107.448	83.03

[Methylene blue] = $3.20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$; [Ascorbic acid] = $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; Temperature = 303 K; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} .

Effect of light intensity :

The intensity of light is measured in terms of mW cm^{-2} with the help of solar intensity meter. It was found that photocurrent show a linear increasing behavior with the increase in light intensity where as photopotential increase in a logarithmic manner. The results are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Effect of light intensity

MB-ascorbic acid system	Light intensity (mW cm^{-2})				
	3.1	5.2	10.4	15.6	26.0
Photopotential (mV)	835.0	862.0	901.0	919.0	948.0
Photocurrent (μA)	154.0	160.0	165.0	172.0	180.0
$\log V$	2.9217	2.9355	2.9547	2.9630	2.9768

[Methylene blue] = $3.20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$; [Ascorbic acid] = $4.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; pH = 13.2; Temperature = 303 K.

Mechanism :

On the basis of above investigations the mechanism of the photocurrent generation in the photogalvanic cell may be proposed as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

At platinum electrode,

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode,

where MB, MB^- , R and R^+ are the dye (methylene blue), its leuco form, reductant (ascorbic acid) and its oxidized form, respectively.

Experimental

A dye methylene blue (Qualigen), a reductant ascorbic acid (ASES) and sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine) were used in the present work. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water and were kept in amber colored containers to protect them from light. A mixture of solution of methylene blue, sodium hydroxide and ascorbic acid were take in a H-type glass tube.

A platinum electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) was immersed in one arm of H-tube and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was kept in other. The arm containing Pt electrode

was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp. A water filter was used to cut off infra-red radiations. A digital pH meter (Systronics) and microammeter (OSAW) were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system, respectively.

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